

INFLUENCE OF THERMALLY INDUCED STRAINS ON SUBSEQUENT CREEP LOADING, USING MICRO RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Jan Schjødt - Thomsen and Ryszard Pyrz

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aalborg University, Pontoppidanstraede 101, 9220 Aalborg East, DENMARK

SUMMARY: This paper considers the influence of thermal strains induced in PP/carbon fibre model composites after manufacturing cycles. Creep loading was applied to dogbone specimens and the fibre creep strains were measured using micro Raman spectroscopy. A theoretical approach is proposed to determine the creep strain in a single embedded fibre. The approach is based upon the integration of pointforces at the interface. These are subsequently used in an incremental approach. It is shown that the model predicts the characteristics of the experiments very well. Generally it is seen that the initial residual stress in the fibre is restricting the magnitude of the fibre strain during subsequent creep loading.

KEYWORDS: Micro Raman spectroscopy, Creep, Residual strains, Point forces, Short fibres.

INTRODUCTION

When a solid is used in a situation which may involve significant loading and deformation it is essential that adequate design should be included in the manufacture of the component.

This may be necessary to ensure efficient material utilisation to prevent unacceptable deformation during service or to avoid failure of the component. In part these design requirements can be met by providing methods for stress and deformation analysis for the relevant material behaviour.

Essentially, this requires some form of theory to model the behaviour, experimental techniques for measuring the material parameters and methods for calculations relevant to the application.

Since the matrix is the load transferring media, it is crucial that a theoretical model describes the field quantities in the matrix properly. The importance of an adequately qualitative description of the field quantities is needed in order to improve the overall performance of the composite, e.g. optimise the creep strength by enhancing interfacial properties.

The main objective in the present study is to investigate the localised creep phenomena from a micromechanical point of view. Similar investigations have been undertaken

by [1] and [2], using an advanced shear-lag model. Finite elements have been used by [3] and [4]. Finally [5], developed a shear lag-like model based on the formalism of continuum damage mechanics.

This paper describes an approach of modelling the stress and strain in a carbon fibre embedded in a polypropylene matrix. The approach is based on the concept of point forces which are integrated along the fibre boundary, thus giving the initial elastic stresses and strains. When the elastic stress and strain field have been obtained an incremental approach is used in order to determine the viscoelastic field quantities [6]. Finally the calculations are compared to the experimentally determined fibre strain.

VISCOELASTIC MODEL

The constitutive model which proved to be very succesfull in describing the mechanical response of many polymers and polymer composites was developed several years ago by [7], based on the notion of internal state variables and the thermodynamics of irreversible processes. Based on the one dimensional Schapery equation and the elastic Hooke's law a three dimensional constitutive model is proposed.

The relation between strains and stresses in the one dimensional case is expressed through the Schapery equation as

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 D_0 \sigma + g_1 \int_0^t \Delta D(\psi - \psi') \frac{\partial g_2(\sigma(\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the nonlinear creep compliance ΔD can be expressed as

$$\Delta D(\psi) = D_1 \psi^n \quad (2)$$

leads to a nonlinear power law expression

$$\varepsilon(t) = \sigma_0 \left(D_0 g_0 + g_1 g_2 D_1 \left(\frac{t}{a_\sigma} \right)^n \right) \quad (3)$$

Experimental creep- and relaxation data for the matrix material are provided by BASF and used for determining the parameters in the Schapery model.

Due to the lack of recovery data it is not possible to separate the three parameters g_1 , g_2 and a_σ . It is therefore decided to assume that g_0 and the product $g_1 g_2$ is equal to unity and thereby placing all the nonlinearity in a_σ . These assumptions are supported by [8-11]. Fig. 1A shows the experimental data for applied loads of 1, 2, ..., 8 MPa along with the creep strains calculated according to Eqn 3.

Relaxation is modelled using the expression

$$\sigma(t) = \varepsilon_0 \left\{ h_e E_e + h_1 h_2 \Delta E \left(\frac{t}{a_\varepsilon} \right) \right\} \quad (4)$$

where a power law is assumed for the nonlinear relaxation modulus, ΔE , leading to

$$\sigma(t) = \varepsilon_0 \left\{ h_e E_e + h_1 h_2 E_1 \left(\frac{t}{a_\varepsilon} \right)^m \right\} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1: Experimental data along with: A) the creep strain equation and B) the relaxation equation

It was found that the best agreement between experimental data and theory was obtained when $a_\varepsilon = 1$, and thereby letting all the nonlinearity be due to h_e and $h_1 h_2$. The experimental data together with Eqn 5, are shown in Fig. 1B. The initial strain corresponds to $\varepsilon_0 = 0.04, 0.08, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1% .

Based on the one dimensional Schapery model and the generalised Hooke's law a three dimensional constitutive expression is formulated.

Defining $\tilde{D}(t)$ as

$$\tilde{D}(t) \equiv \left(D_0 g_0 + g_1 g_2 D_1 \left(\frac{t}{a_\sigma} \right)^n \right) \quad (6)$$

and substituting the nonlinear creep compliance into Hooke's law and assuming that Poisson's ratio is independent of time or at least a weak function of time, the creep strains are obtained as

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(t) = \tilde{D}(t)(1 + \nu_m)\sigma_{ij} - \tilde{D}(t)\nu_m\delta_{ij}\sigma_{kk} \quad (7)$$

in which a_σ is now a function of Von Mises effective stress. This equation is valid for any isotropic, time dependent material subjected to a constant applied load, [12].

The same approach is used when considering the variation of the stress with time. Defining $\tilde{E}(t)$ as

$$\tilde{E}(t) \equiv (h_e E_e + h_1 h_2 E_1 (t)^m) \quad (8)$$

the time dependent stress becomes

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = \frac{\tilde{E}(t)}{1 + \nu_m} \left(\varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu_m}{1 - 2\nu_m} \delta_{ij} \varepsilon_{kk} \right) \quad (9)$$

where h_e and $h_1 h_2$ now are functions of Von Mises effective strain.

The complete stress field is obtained by integrating the tractions along the fibre boundary. The complete stress field is inserted into the three dimensional constitutive equation, Eqn 7, for $t = 0$, thus giving the initial elastic strain, ε^e . This strain causes stress relaxation during a time step dt , resulting in a new state of stress $\sigma_{ij} + d\sigma_{ij}$ to be used in the next time

increment together with $t = dt$, causing a new state of strain which again causes stress relaxation and so on. This is repeated until t is equal to the desired time of duration. The incremental strains are found by differentiating Eqn 7 with respect to time and are given as

$$d\varepsilon_{ij} = \{(1 + \nu_m)\sigma_{ij} - \nu_m\sigma_{kk}\delta_{ij}\} \frac{\partial \tilde{D}(t)}{\partial t} dt \quad (10)$$

where it is assumed that the stress is constant during the time increment dt . The time varying incremental stress are obtained in the same manner as

$$d\sigma_{ij} = \frac{1}{1 + \nu_m} \left\{ \varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu_m}{1 - 2\nu_m} \delta_{ij} \varepsilon_{kk} \right\} \frac{\partial \tilde{E}(t)}{\partial t} dt \quad (11)$$

where it is assumed that the strains are constant during the time increment.

SINGLE FIBRE CREEP MODELLING

In this section the theoretical approach is described, from which the stress and strain in the matrix and fibre can be obtained at any desired time during creep. The approach is inspired by [13].

In the present analysis different Poisson ratios, transversely isotropic fibres as well as thermal effects are considered. An approximate elastic solution based on Eshelby's thought experiment is used to provide the initial elastic stress state.

Fig. 2: The loading situation.

A transversely isotropic fibre of length l_f and diameter d_f is embedded in an infinite initially elastic matrix with Young's modulus E_m and Poisson's ratio ν_m . The system is subjected to tensile stresses σ_x^∞ at the remote boundary as shown in Fig. 2.

An exact solution to the problem of a cylindrical fibre of finite length embedded in an infinite matrix is very difficult to obtain but a useful and reasonably accurate solution is obtainable by means of Eshelby's thought experiment.

The interfacial tractions are obtained as follows. The fibre is removed from the infinitely extended matrix and replaced by matrix material. σ_x^∞ , σ_y^∞ and a temperature field are applied, causing strains ε_x^∞ and ε_y^∞ . The matrix material occupying the position of the fibre is removed and surface tractions, σ_x^∞ and σ_y^∞ are placed along the boundary of the "hole", as shown in Fig. 3A.

Tractions of magnitudes $\varepsilon_x^\infty E_f^l$ are applied to the ends of the fibre and $\varepsilon_y^\infty E_f^t$ are applied

Fig. 3: Tractions A) on the matrix and B) on the fibre

to the sides of the fibre in order to make it fit perfectly into the deformed hole of the matrix. The traction applied to the end of the fibre causes additionally transverse stresses of magnitude $-\nu_f^t \epsilon_x^\infty E_f^l$. Furthermore the transverse traction, $\epsilon_y^\infty E_f^t$, causes a longitudinal stress of magnitude $-\epsilon_y^\infty E_f^t \nu_f^l$, Fig. 3B. The additional longitudinal stress, $-\epsilon_y^\infty E_f^t \nu_f^l$, will make yet another contribution to the transverse stress but this is neglected since it contains higher order terms of Poisson's ratios, such as $\nu_m \nu_f^l$.

The interfacial tractions - incorporating thermal contributions - in the composite when the fibre is put back into the matrix are now readily obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x^* &= -\sigma_x^\infty + \left(\frac{\sigma_x^\infty}{E_m} - \epsilon^{th}\right)E_f^l - \left(\frac{\sigma_y^\infty}{E_m} - \epsilon^{th}\right)E_f^t \nu_f^l \\ \sigma_y^* &= -\sigma_y^\infty + \left(\frac{\sigma_y^\infty}{E_m} - \epsilon^{th}\right)E_f^t - \left(\frac{\sigma_x^\infty}{E_m} - \epsilon^{th}\right)E_f^l \nu_f^t\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

where $\epsilon^{th} = \alpha \Delta T$. In this equation the only thermal contributions are due to the matrix. The contributions from the fibre are neglected since $\alpha_m \gg \alpha_f$. In this case when uniaxial load is considered σ_y^∞ is simply set equal to zero.

From [14], it is known that a force P acting in the x -direction at a point (x_0, y_0) in an infinite plate creates the stresses σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} given by

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x(x, y) &= \frac{P}{4\pi} \frac{(x - x_0)}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \left\{ -(3 + \nu) + 2(1 + \nu) \frac{(y - y_0)^2}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \right\} \\ \sigma_y(x, y) &= \frac{P}{4\pi} \frac{(x - x_0)}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \left\{ (1 - \nu) - 2(1 + \nu) \frac{(y - y_0)^2}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \right\} \\ \tau_{xy}(x, y) &= \frac{P}{4\pi} \frac{(y - y_0)}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \left\{ (1 - \nu) + 2(1 + \nu) \frac{(x - x_0)^2}{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

Eqn 13 are used to find the stress in the matrix material after rewriting them and replacing P by the interfacial tractions.

If the tractions in Eqn 12 are used as they are and applied directly on the matrix at the

interface they will cause an incompatible displacement field. So in order to ensure compatibility the stress-strain relations and the strain-displacement relations are combined to yield

$$\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{E'_m} (\sigma_x - \nu'_m \sigma_y) \quad \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{E'_m} (\sigma_y - \nu'_m \sigma_x) \quad (14)$$

where E'_m and ν'_m depends on whether the deformation state is plane stress or plane strain. In the present analysis the plane strain situation is considered. The stress in the matrix material due to the interfacial tractions are obtained by rewriting Eqn 13 to give the stress in an infinite plane due to a point force in the x -direction at $(x, y) = (\pm l_f/2, 0)$ and a point force in the y -direction at $(x, y) = (0, \pm d_f/2)$, respectively. Now u_x and u_y are readily found by inserting the stress from the integration into the stress-displacement relations, Eqn 14, and integrating with respect to x and y , respectively. Since the displacements u_x and u_y are singular for $(x, y) = (\pm l_f/2, 0)$ and $(x, y) = (0, \pm d_f/2)$, average displacements across the fibre end and along the sides of the fibre are defined as

$$\langle u_x \rangle = \frac{2}{d_f} \int_0^{d_f/2} u_x dy$$

$$\langle u_y \rangle = \frac{2}{l_f} \int_0^{l_f/2} u_y dx$$

These average displacements are non-singular at $x = \pm l_f/2$ and $y = \pm d_f/2$. $\langle u_x \rangle$ and $\langle u_y \rangle$ gives the average displacements due to a force P and can be rearranged to give the displacement due to a unit force dP . The relation between the displacements $\langle u_x \rangle$ and $\langle u_y \rangle$ and the unit force dP can be thought of as being the stiffness of the infinite medium in the x - and y -direction, respectively. These stiffnesses are obtained as

$$K_x^m = \frac{dP}{d\langle u_x \rangle} \quad K_y^m = \frac{dP}{d\langle u_y \rangle} \quad (15)$$

Now the stiffnesses of the matrix and the fibre are used to determine the fraction of the interfacial force which is carried by the fibre and matrix, respectively. The fraction of the interfacial force carried by the matrix in the x - and y -direction are denoted as ΔP_x^m and ΔP_y^m and are determined as

$$\Delta P_i^m = K_i^m \Delta u_i$$

The compatible tractions to be integrated along the fibre/matrix boundary are now obtained as

$$\sigma_x^{int} = -\frac{\sigma_x^* K_m^x}{K_x^m + K_x^f} \quad \sigma_y^{int} = -\frac{\sigma_y^* K_m^y}{K_y^m + K_y^f} \quad (16)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical model shown previously have been used to calculate the fibre strains after 3 hours creep at three load levels corresponding to 1, 4 and 8 MPa. The fibre in the

model has a length of $450\ \mu\text{m}$, which corresponds to the average fibre length found in all the investigated specimens. All the calculated values are only shown for half the fibre length since it is symmetric. In the theoretical calculations it is assumed that the fibre is perfectly bonded to the matrix.

The fibre strain has been measured using micro Raman spectroscopy. The fibre strains are measured in discrete points along the length of the fibre thereby giving the strain profile in the fibre. The initial residual strains - due to manufacture of the specimen - are measured before any load is applied. Creep loading conditions is applied to the specimen by a purpose made straining rig mounted on the microscope. The straining rig is force controlled and operated by a PC.

Fig. 4: Fibre strain A) calculated and B) measured

In Fig. 4B the measured fibre strains are shown. The embedded fibre has a length of $500\ \mu\text{m}$. The residual strains are building up in a nearly linear manner until the middle of the fibre where the strain levels off. The magnitude of the measured fibre strain is close to the compressive fracture strain of the used carbon fibres. After 3 hours of creep at a load of 1 MPa, the measured fibre strains are nearly constant, but below zero. The fact that the strains in the fibre are compressive after 3 hours of creep indicates that this load level and the overall matrix creep strains are not sufficient to create tension in the fibre. In Fig. 4A the calculated fibre strains are shown. Here, it is important to notice that the magnitudes of the calculated strains and the experimentally measured strains can not be compared directly because the calculations are based on a plane strain assumption. However, the tendencies are obvious. The calculated fibre strain is also compressive after 3 hours of creep at 1 MPa load. The rate at which the fibre strains are building up is higher for the calculated fibre strain than for the measured fibre strain. This is due to the fact that the interfacial tractions are assumed to be constant. The constant interfacial tractions affect the interfacial shear stress which are governing the shape of the fibre strain profile.

In Fig. 5B the measured fibre strains are shown. The embedded fibre has a length of $400\ \mu\text{m}$. Again the residual fibre strain builds up linearly towards the middle of the fibre where it abruptly changes slope and decreases towards the other end of the fibre. The fibre strains after 3 hours of creep at 4 MPa is seen to increase in a slightly nonlinear

Fig. 5: Fibre strain A) calculated and B) measured

manner but only reaches a maximum value of approximately zero in spite of the fact that the overall strain after 3 hours of creep is 0.64 %. In the region below 50 μm the shape of the strain resembles what is seen from elastic analysis as in [15]. In Fig. 5A the calculated fibre strains are shown. Again the characteristics of the experiment is displayed in the calculations. The fibre strain after 3 hours creep is just above zero. An interesting aspect to notice is that the model predicts both compression and tension in the fibre after 3 hours of loading.

Fig. 6: Fibre strain A) calculated and B) measured

In Fig. 6B the measured fibre strains are shown. The embedded fibre has a length of 350 μm . The residual fibre strains are building up in a nearly linear manner and abruptly changes slope at the middle of the fibre. The strain after 3 hours of creep at 8 MPa is now positive in the middle of the fibre and still negative at the end, where the strain profile is very nonlinear. In Fig. 6A the calculated fibre strain is shown. The characteristics of the experiment is predicted by the model. However, all of the fibre is in tension, whereas

the experiment shows compression at the end of the fibre. This difference may again be due to the assumption of the constant interfacial tractions.

CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical model based upon Eshelby's thought experiment and the integration of interfacial tractions has been shown. In the model it is assumed that the interfacial tractions are constant. Comparisons have been made between the predictions from the model and experimental fibre strains measured by micro Raman spectroscopy.

The magnitudes of the fibre strains calculated from the model are not directly comparable to experiment because the model assumes plane strain. The nature of the tractions controls the form of the interfacial shear stress which govern the shape of the longitudinal fibre stress profile. As a consequence the rates at which the strain is building up in the fibre are different when comparing calculations and experiments. However, the characteristics of the experiments are reflected in the theoretical predictions.

Generally it is seen that the initial residual stress in the fibre is restricting the level of the fibre strain during subsequent creep loading.

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